

The Impact of Using Palarong Pinoy “ABAKALaro at Matuto Program” in the Phonological Awareness and Reading Skills of Selected Kindergarten Pupils

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ABSTRACT: Making children learn how to read is one of the primary goals of every preschool teacher. Making the, enjoy and love to read is another thing. The purpose of this study is to make every participant a reader before reaching Grade 1 through ABAKALaro at Matuto Program. The program provides series of reading activities using palarongpinoy. Indigenous games in the Philippines (PalarongPinoy) have been part of the Filipino but due to the rise of technology, many children nowadays were not aware how to play them.

Through ABAKALaro at Matuto Program, selected preschool pupils improved their reading skills while having enjoyable moments with their sibling, parents or relatives.

The result of the study showed an increase of reading progress among the 83 selected kindergarten pupils of Pinagbuhatan Elementary School.

Keyword: Pay-based learning, palarongpinoy, educational games, preschool

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching young children to read is essential in developing their language skills; it builds vocabulary and a better understanding of the cultures. Play is an integral part of child development. Research shows that play-based learning enhances children’s academic and developmental learning outcomes. It can also set your child up for success in the 21st century by teaching them relevant skills.(Robinson, 2018 et al.). Piaget advocate for helping students understand learning as a lifelong process of discovery and joy. Play plays a vital role in education.

Filipino students ranked last among 79 countries in a global survey of reading comprehension, and Data from the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) 2019 showed the percentage of Grade 5 Filipino students who achieved minimum proficiency in reading, writing, and mathematics was significantly lower than Vietnam and Malaysia. Fifth-graders in the Philippines were at par or sometimes even worse than those in Cambodia but performed slightly better than those in Laos and Myanmar. This article showed how poor the reading skills of Filipino children are.

Our school advocates the reading program. In fact, there are reading intervention programs in every grade level such as our school such as Drop Everything and Read (DEAR), Summer Reading Camp, Read my hat, and more, but it seems not enough to make our pupils readers.

The primary goal is to alleviate the reading problems in our school by mastering the phonics and being able to read as early as Kindergarten in way children would enjoy. The objective of this study is to introduce the

ABAKAlaro at MATUTO program to the selected Kindergarten pupils. This program does not only promote phonological awareness and reading skills but also introduces the larongPinoy as part of our culture which is now being forgotten due to computers and technology.

The larongPinoy could also be done indoors. Piko, Pitik- Bulag, Teks, LuksongTinik and Tagu-taguan could be play even in small area or inside the home. The materials are easily accessible and available at home. Materials could be made of old folders or cardboard, old notebooks, scratch papers, pens, markers, chalk, or charcoal. With the help of ABAKAlaro at MATUTO program, it eases the burdens of the parents in forcing their children to study and practice reading for children considers it as a game which they love to do. The program also promotes family bonding in an educational way.

PROPOSED INNOVATION, INTERVENTION AND STRATEGY

The ABAKAlaro at MATUTO program consist of five palarongpinoy with a twist namely Piko, Teks, Pitik-Bulag, Luksong-Tinik and Tagu-taguan. The participants will play the palarongpinoy with a family member/s.

The selected kindergarten pupils must be able to say the letters and sounds or read the syllable/ word written on the fingers, floor, paper, and cards depending on the kind of larongPinoy in order to win the game. In this way, they will be able to recognize the letters, master the sound, and a good start to blend letters and become syllable readers to word readers as early as Kindergarten. Every time they win, it develops the child's self-esteem and later on becomes a reader, which will help decrease the number of non-readers in our school.

The researchers will orient the parents about the purpose of the program, mechanics, and how ABAKAlaro at MATUTO Program is being administered at home. The researchers assured of the confidentiality of their child's data and information for those who are willing to participate in the program. There will be a guided home-based activity and reflection of the parents every month. The ABAKAlaro at MATUTO Program will have its Parents Orientation on the first week of December, and the implementation follows on the Month of January up to a month of May. Each ParalongPinoy will be administered every month. Data Collection will be in the month of June after administering all the PalarongPinoy.

NAME	OBJECTIVES	MATERIALS	MECHANICS
1. Pitik – Bulag 	To recognize the letter and sound written on the upper part of the finger.	Pens / Markers	The parent / sibling will write on the upper part of their fingers the letters which they tackled that day. They will stand/sit facing their partner. The child will be asked to cover his eyes, the parent / sibling will poke his partner with one of his chosen fingers. The child who covered his eyes will guess which finger his partner used in poking him. Instead of saying the part of the fingers, they must say the letter and sound written on the upper part of the finger. If the answer is wrong, they exchange the roles in the game.

<p>2. Piko</p>	<p>To recognize the letter and sound written on each box.</p>	<p>Chalk . Charcoal or any writing materials available at home.</p>	<p>The parent will draw the pattern on the floor using chalk / charcoal or any materials available at home Instead of numbers, letters will be written inside each box. The parent will first take their turn to show the procedure of the game. The child must tell the letters while stepping on the box. Wrong answer will lose a turn.</p>
<p>3. Teks</p>	<p>To recognize the letter and sound written on each card.</p>	<p>Old cardboard/ folders pens/ markers</p>	<p>The parent will make the text cards using old folders or any old materials available at home. These playing cards contain the different letters. They are played by tossing them to the air until the cards hit the ground. The cards are flipped upwards through the air using the thumb and the forefinger which creates a snapping sound as the nail of the thumb hits the surface of the ground. The winner must identify the letters in the flipped card in order to collect the cards.</p>
<p>4. Taguan</p>	<p>To recognize the letter and sound written on shirt.</p>	<p>Scratch paper markers scatch-tape or clip</p>	<p>The parent will write the letter on the paper and attach it on the their shirt. The child will face the door, covering his face while counting 1 to 10. (numeracy skills) During counting's, the parent and siblings will hide wherever it could be behind the cabinet, under the table etc. The child will look for the participants (mother and siblings) and once caught he has to say "BOOM" followed by the letter written on the shirt he caught and run going back to his base.</p>
<p>5. Luksong-Tinik</p>	<p>To recognize the letter and sound written on the palm and soles.</p>	<p>Pens / markers</p>	<p>The parent will write the letters on the palm and sole of all the participants. Two players serve as the base of the tinik by putting their right or left feet together (soles touching gradually building the tinik). A starting point is set by all the players, giving enough runway for all the players to achieve a higher jump. Before they jump, they must identity first the letters written on the soles and palm of the players who serve as a base before they jump.</p>

ACTION RESEACH QUESTIONS

1. How does Abakalaro at Matuto Program help in the phonological awareness and reading skills of the selected Kindergarten pupils?
2. What are the effects of Abakalaro Program to the learners at home?
3. How effective is the use of ABAKAlaro at MATUTO Program in making Kindergarten readers?

ACTION RESEACH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This is a descriptive research design that looked into the impact of ABAKAlaro at MATUTO Program to selected kindergarten pupils of Pinagbuhatan Elementary School in their phonological awareness, reading skills and speed.

Conceptual Framework

There were 83 participants in the program. The researchers explained and demonstrated the mechanics of each PalarongPinoy before the parents administered it to their children. They asked the parents' weekly about the performance of the children during the game.

Reading level and reading speed were monitored after each session via vide call.

The data from the pre-test and post-test were analyzed through the use Z-test to show significant differences in the pre and post-test results.

Participants and/other sources of Data and Information

All participants selected for this study are studying at Pinagbuhatan Elementary School. There will be 38 boys and 45 girls Kindergarten pupils who will participate in this study. They belong to the researchers' class.

Data Gathering

The researchers asked permission from the principal then sought instrument validation from master teachers. The pre-test and post-test were scheduled and conducted. The data from pre and post-test of those pupils were compared. Z-Test were used to analyze the result.

Analysis

All the collected data were charted, tallied, analyzed and treated statistically to find out the effectiveness of the ABAKAlaro at Matuto Program in the Phonological awareness and Reading skills of the selected Kindergarten pupils.

Figure 1
 READING LEVEL BEFORE AND AFTER THE PROGRAM

Figure 2
 READING LEVEL BEFORE AND AFTER THE PROGRAM

Figure 4
 Pretest and Post Test result

Table 1

	PRE-TEST	POST TEST
mean	11.3975904	26.6428571
percentage of mastery	11	28

The table shows the Pre and Post-test mean, and percentage of mastery level of the participants before and after the program.. The result of the pre and post test showed that there was significant difference between the result of the score of the pupils before and after the program.

To test the significance difference of the two mean scores we used Z-Test for independent sample. The result is significant at 0.05 level of significance or 95%, the result falls between -10.730884 and 1.959963985 this result signifies that there is a substantial difference in the test result after intervention that increase the performance of kinder pupils academically.

We used Z-Test to determine the result of pre-test and post test mean are different when the variances are known and the sample size is large.

Result and Discussion

The tables and figures shows the reading level, reading speed and the Pre and Post-test mean, and percentage of mastery level of the participants before and after the program. The reading level graph and the reading speed graph showed a significant difference in the performance of the participants before and after the program. The mean score of Pre-test is 11.3975904 and the mastery level is 11 while Post-test is 26.6428571 and the mastery level is 28.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study showed the huge difference between the reading level, reading speed and test results of the participants before and after ABAKALaro at Matuto Program. Collaborating with parents in teaching their child, literacy and numeracy, is one of the most effective ways to make education possible in this new normal. Truly, children learn best when they are having fun.

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